

PREVALENCE OF MUSCULAR ASTHENOPIA AND ITS IMPACT ON QUALITY OF LIFE IN STUDENTS OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES SARHAD UNIVERSITY PESHAWAR, USING MOBILE.

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Abstract

BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVE: Prolonged use of digital devices has led to a rise in asthenopia, commonly known as digital eye strain, characterized by visual discomfort and fatigue. This study explores the prevalence of muscular asthenopia and its impact on the quality of life among Allied Health Sciences students at Sarhad University of Science and Information Technology, Peshawar, in relation to excessive mobile phone use.

METHODOLOGY: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted using non-probability convenience sampling. Data were collected from 351 undergraduate students aged between 18 and 28 years through the ASQ-17 (Asthenopia Survey Questionnaire). Statistical analysis of the collected data was performed using SPSS Version 20.

RESULTS: Statistical analysis found that among 351 participants, 74.9% were male, and the average age was 20.87 years. A majority of students (89.7%) used Android phones, and 53.8% reported using their mobile phones for 4 to 6 hours daily. Muscular asthenopia was diagnosed in 51.3% of the students. Commonly reported symptoms included eye discomfort, dryness, and concentration difficulties. Extended screen time and a lack of awareness about eye health were found to be major contributing factors. These findings align with global research linking excessive mobile phone use to both visual and cognitive strain.

CONCLUSION: The study concludes that muscular asthenopia is common among university students due to prolonged mobile phone use. To address this issue, preventive education, limiting screen time, and promoting eye care strategies such as the 20-20-20 rule are essential for protecting visual health and supporting academic performance.

INTRODUCTION

In both daily life and school, electronic gadgets like computers, tablets, and smartphones have become indispensable. Even while these tools are meant to make learning easier and more efficient, improper

usage of them might have unfavorable effects(1, 2). Globally, internet users log on for roughly 6 hours and 31 minutes every day on average(3).The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated this trend by shifting work,

education, and social interactions online. As a result, daily screen time has significantly increased worldwide, contributing to visual and physical discomfort(4).

Asthenopia is now so frequently caused by prolonged use of computers and other digital devices that it has been termed "computer vision syndrome" or "digital eyestrain"(5). Digital eye strain (DES), another name for computer vision syndrome (CVS), is a group of symptoms brought on by extended and continuous usage of computers or other electronic devices(6). With presumably expanded usage of computers and its related input devices, this well-known clinical object gains major importance. The ocular component of the syndrome includes asthenopia and symptoms associated with dry eye disease. Additionally, there are negative impacts on the musculoskeletal system, skin, nervous system, and mind associated with using various digital devices(7). Eye strain, eye tiredness, eye pain, blurred vision, double vision, dry eyes, stinging itching, red eyes, headache, and neck and shoulder pain are the most prevalent ocular and non-ocular problems linked to CVS or digital eyestrain(5). These symptoms arise due to high visual demands, poor ergonomics, and reduced blink rates during screen use(8, 9).

Using a computer or digital screen might cause vision-related issues because of its special features and high visual demands. Untreated vision problems might exacerbate the severity of CVS(9). Computer use requires different viewing angles and distances, and issues like glare, reflections, and poor contrast can worsen symptoms. Uncorrected vision problems, poor lighting, and screen glare can lead to CVS, but regular eye care and better screen habits can reduce symptoms(10). Poor posture, improper chair placement, screen glare, and bad lighting can cause eye strain, headaches, and discomfort. These ergonomic issues may lead to long-term problems like neck and back pain. Addressing them is vital for a healthy and productive workspace(11).

Digital Eye Strain (DES) can be detected or diagnosed in practice using a variety of techniques that emphasize close communication with the patient and careful research. Patients often tell their optometrist or Certified Lens Optician (CLO) about their DES symptoms during an appointment. If the practitioner concludes that the patient is in 3 fact

suffering from the effects of DES, it is necessary for them to offer thorough advice on how to mitigate these symptoms(12).

Computer Vision Syndrome (CVS) requires a comprehensive approach that includes both eye care and adjustments to the user's environment and habits to effectively reduce symptoms and prevent further discomfort(5). Preventive strategies include the 20-20-20 rule (look 20 feet away for 20 seconds every 20 minutes), proper screen positioning, and regular breaks(13).

Computer Vision Syndrome (CVS) is a rising global occupational health issue annually(14), affecting over 60 to 70 million people worldwide, with one million new cases reported(15). Asthenopia affects 46.3% of computer users in India, compared to 31.9% in Italy, 68.5% in Mexico, and 63.4% in Australia(1). Global reports on the prevalence of CVS range from 12.1% to 94.8% in children and from 35.2% to 97.3% in adults(16-18). Studies show that medical students at a university in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia(19), and IT professionals(20) are particularly at risk due to prolonged digital exposure. Women were more susceptible to CVS during the pandemic than students because they assisted their kids with online education(21). Despite its high occurrence, public awareness and preventive practices for CVS remain insufficient(22).

As education moves toward digital learning, students now spend many hours daily in front of screens, especially during exams. This long screen time increases the risk of Asthenopia (eye strain), which can lead to stress and anxiety if not managed early. This study aims to find out how common Asthenopia is among students and raise awareness about it. It also suggests using the 20-20-20 rule: after every 20 minutes of screen use, close your eyes for 20 seconds and look at something 20 feet away to help prevent eye strain.

Methods

This study used a descriptive cross-sectional design to find out the prevalence of muscular asthenopia and its impact on quality Data were collected over six months in 2025. The research was conducted at multiple department of Sarhad University of sciences and information technology Peshawar. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional

Research Committee (IRC), and informed consent was secured from all participants before the data collection. Only face-to-face interactions were used to reach participants.

A non-probability convenience sampling technique was adopted, selecting individuals who were readily available and willing to participate. The minimum sample size was calculated using RaoSoft, Inc., with a 5% margin of error, 95% confidence level, and 50% response distribution, resulting in a recommended sample of at least 351 participants. Inclusion criteria included Individuals of both genders (male and female), Students enrolled in SIAHS, Age ranging from 18 to 28 years and Undergraduate students. Exclusion criteria included Staff members, Security guards, Students who are not mobile users and Students who do not want to be the part of data collection process.

For data collection, the ASQ-17 questionnaire was used. This 17-item, questionnaire assesses asthenopia covering eye symptoms(7 items), visual symptoms(6

items) and systemic and psychological symptoms(4 items). Each item is rated on a Likert scale (0 = no, 1 = mild, 2 = moderate, 3 = severe), with total scores 51 and cut off value is 12.5. Demographic data were also collected alongside the ASQ-17 responses. Data were analyzed using SPSS software, with frequency tables, charts, and graphs generated to present results clearly and professionally.

RESULTS:
DEMOGRAPHICS

The study included 351 students (N=327) selected from Sarhad University Peshawar. Participants with an age range of 17 to 27 years (M = 20.87, SD = 1.967), 263 were male (74.9%) and 88 were females(25.1%) out of 351. Additionally most 315 (89.7%) used Android phones, while only 36 (10.3%) used iPhones, showing a strong preference for Android devices(Table 1)

Table 1: Demographics of the participants:

Age of research participants		Gender of research participants		Mobile use by participants	
N	351	351		351	
	0	0		0	
Mean	20.87	Males	263	Android Phones	315
		Females	88	iPhones	36
Std.Deviation	1.967				

Among 351 participants, 189 (53.8%) used mobile phones for 4 to 6 hours daily, 67 (19.1%) for 7 to 9

hours, and 95 (27.1%) for more than 9 hours. (Table 2)

Table 2: Duration of Mobile Use

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
4 to 6 hours	189	53.8	53.8	53.8
7 to 9 hours	67	19.1	19.1	72.9
Valid greater than 9 hours	95	27.1	27.1	100.0
Total	351	100.0	100.0	

Asthenopia level

Among 351 participants, 171 (48.7%) had no asthenopia (below 12.5), while 180 (51.3%) experienced asthenopia (above 12.5). (FIGURE 1)

Figure 1: level of Asthenopia

Discussion

The findings of current study revealed that more than half of the Allied Health Sciences students (51.3%) at Sarhad University experienced muscular asthenopia. Most participants used Android phones (89.7%). Regarding mobile usage, over half (53.8%) used their phones for 4 to 6 hours daily, potentially increasing the risk of eye strain. Common symptoms included eye discomfort (45.0%), eye dryness (29.6%), and eye pain (43.6%), with many reporting sensations like heavy eyelids (50.1%) and tight eyes (46.2%). Notably, 51.3% experienced asthenopia, characterized by symptoms such as blurred vision, reduced concentration, and difficulty remembering. These findings highlight the potential impact of prolonged mobile use on eye health, emphasizing the need for awareness and preventive measures to reduce eye strain and related symptoms.

These results are supported by various international studies. For example, a study conducted at the University of Sunderland found that students who used digital screens for more than six hours daily reported frequent headaches and cognitive strain, including difficulty focusing and memory problems(23). Similarly, Pavel et al. (2024) conducted a study across medical universities in Lasi, Paris, and other European cities, which found that 68.9% of Romanian medical students experienced blurred vision, and symptoms like eye fatigue were common in France and England. These symptoms were directly linked to prolonged screen exposure(24).

However, our findings differ from a study by Azlan et al. (2024), which showed that many students had good awareness about Computer Vision Syndrome (CVS) and took preventive measures. As a result, they mostly reported musculoskeletal symptoms like neck or back pain, rather than visual issues. In

contrast, our participants reported more visual symptoms, possibly because they did not follow preventive practices, even if they were aware of them. This suggests that having knowledge is not enough—students need to actively apply protective strategies, such as taking breaks, adjusting screen brightness, and maintaining proper posture(25).

Overall, this study highlights that prolonged mobile phone use is strongly associated with visual discomfort and eye fatigue. Without proper awareness and preventive actions, these symptoms can negatively affect students' quality of life, academic performance, and mental focus. Therefore, promoting digital eye health and good screen habits among students is essential.

Conclusion

The study investigated the prevalence of muscular asthenopia among students of Allied Health Sciences at Sarhad University, focusing on the impact of excessive mobile use on their quality of life. The findings revealed that prolonged screen time significantly contributes to eye strain, visual discomfort, and other related symptoms, which can negatively affect both academic performance and overall well-being. Despite the widespread use of digital devices, awareness about proper usage and preventive measures remains limited among students. This lack of awareness, combined with improper screen habits, leads to a high incidence of muscular asthenopia. It is essential to address these challenges to improve students' quality of life and academic outcomes.

Limitation of the study:

There are several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings of this study. Firstly, the cross-sectional nature of the

research limits the ability to determine cause-and-effect relationships, as data were collected at a single point in time, making it difficult to assess which variables preceded others. Secondly, the study was conducted at a single center, specifically among undergraduate students of the School of Allied Health Sciences (SIAHS) at Sarhad University, which restricts the generalizability of the results to other populations or educational settings. The limited sample may not be the representative of other demographics groups or educational settings. Additionally, the study relied on self-reported data, which introduces the possibility of recall bias, as participants may not accurately remember or may misreport their symptoms and behaviors. Moreover, the study did not account for all potential confounding factors that could influence the outcomes, thereby limiting the ability to isolate the effects of individual variables. Finally, due to the nature of the design, it was not possible to observe changes over time or identify the incidence of new cases, which could provide deeper insight into the progression of the condition.

REFERENCES

1. Al Tawil L, Aldokhayel S, Zeitouni L, Qadoumi T, Hussein S, Ahamed SS. Prevalence of self-reported computer vision syndrome symptoms and its associated factors among university students. *European journal of ophthalmology*. 2020;30(1):189-95.
2. Hassan HAG. Computer vision syndrome among medical students at the University of Khartoum, Sudan: prevalence and associated factors. *Cureus*. 2023;15(5).
3. Alkousheh H, Alkousheh Y, Qawaqzeh R, Al Juneidi L, Al-Zerikat L, Hussain A, et al. The hidden cost of digital learning: a cross-sectional study assessing the prevalence of computer vision syndrome (CVS) among medical students in Jordan. *BMJ open*. 2025;15(1):e093939.
4. Agarwal R, Tripathi A, Khan IA, Agarwal M. Effect of increased screen time on eyes during COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*. 2022;11(7):3642-7.
5. Aghaei H, Abdolalizadeh P. Computer vision syndrome. *Recent Advances in Dry Eye Disease: IntechOpen*; 2023.
6. Dostálová N, Vrubel M, Kachlík P. Computer vision syndrome-symptoms and prevention. *Casopis lekaru ceskych*. 2021;160(2-3):88-92.
7. Ranasinghe P, Wathurapatha W, Perera Y, Lamabadusuriya D, Kulatunga S, Jayawardana N, et al. Computer vision syndrome among computer office workers in a developing country: an evaluation of prevalence and risk factors. *BMC research notes*. 2016;9(1):150.
8. Choi JH, Li Y, Kim SH, Jin R, Kim YH, Choi W, et al. The influences of smartphone use on the status of the tear film and ocular surface. *PloS one*. 2018;13(10):e0206541.
9. Ortiz-Toquero S, Sanchez I, Serrano A, Martin R. Prevalence of computer vision syndrome and its risk factors in a Spanish university population. *Eye & Contact Lens*. 2024;50(8):333-41.
10. Rosenfield M. Computer vision syndrome: a review of ocular causes and potential treatments. *Ophthalmic and Physiological Optics*. 2011;31(5):502-15.
11. Kolbe O, Degle S. Presbyopic personal computer work: a comparison of progressive addition lenses for general purpose and personal computer work. *Optometry and Vision Science*. 2018;95(11):1046-53.
12. Moore PA. Digital eye strain.
13. A Salem F, M Weheida S, Abdel Ghafar Ali K, Mohamed Metwely S, Alkordy A, Y El Emam S, et al. Computer Vision Syndrome as Perceived by Undergraduate Nursing Students Versus Clinical Nursing Teachers. *Egyptian Journal of Health Care*. 2023;14(4):399-418.

14. Shahid E, Burhany T, Siddique WA, Fasih U, Shaikh A. Frequency of computer vision syndrome in computer users. *Pakistan Journal of Ophthalmology*. 2017;33(2).
15. Das A, Shah S, Adhikari TB, Paudel BS, Sah SK, Das RK, et al. Computer vision syndrome, musculoskeletal, and stress-related problems among visual display terminal users in Nepal. *PLoS One*. 2022;17(7):e0268356.
16. Altalhi A, Khayyat W, Khojah O, Alsalmi M, Almarzouki H. Computer vision syndrome among health sciences students in Saudi Arabia: prevalence and risk factors. *Cureus*. 2020;12(2).
17. Li L, Zhang J, Chen M, Li X, Chu Q, Jiang R, et al. Contribution of total screen/online-course time to asthenopia in children during COVID-19 pandemic via influencing psychological stress. *Frontiers in Public Health*. 2021;9:736617.
18. Selvaraj S, Ganesan DK, Jain T. A study on single versus multiple symptoms of computer vision syndrome (CVS) among engineering students in Kancheepuram District, Tamil Nadu. *International Journal of Current Research and Review*. 2021;13(6):51-5.
19. Maneea MWB, Alamawi HO, Almuqbil A, Abukhlaled JK, Alsuwailem G, Alabdulminaim Jr J, et al. Digital Eye Straining: Exploring Its Prevalence, Associated Factors, and Effects on the Quality of Life. *Cureus*. 2024;16(5).
20. Zayed HAM, Saied SM, Younis EA, Atlam SA. Digital eye strain: prevalence and associated factors among information technology professionals, Egypt. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 2021;28(20):25187-95.
21. Abusamak M, Jaber HM, Alrawashdeh HM. The effect of lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic on digital eye strain symptoms among the general population: a cross-sectional survey. *Frontiers in public health*. 2022;10:895517.
22. Almalki AM, Alblowi M, Aldosari AM, Khandekar R, Al-Swailem SA. Population perceived eye strain due to digital devices usage during COVID-19 pandemic. *International Ophthalmology*. 2023;43(6):1935-43.
23. Ekuase AU, Mdegela M, Ihedike C. The potential association between asthenopia and its risk factors amongst students at the University of Sunderland. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research and Studies*. 2024;4(6):525-32.
24. Pavel IA, BOGDANICI CM, Donica V, BOGDANICI CG. VISION AND LIFE QUALITY: A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON STUDENTS FROM MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES. *The Medical-Surgical Journal*. 2024;128(4):766-73.
25. Azlan NZ, Kamaruddin A, Othman N, Isa MLM. Knowledge and awareness on computer vision syndrome (cvs) and their contributing factor among undergraduate university students. *Malaysian Journal of Public Health Medicine*. 2024;24(1):215-24. intoxication. *PLoS One*, 13(10), e0203602